

```

from picamera2 import Picamera2, Preview
import time
from libcamera import controls
import cv2 as cv
import numpy as np

LP = 0

def ImageAnalysis(path):
    cCenter = (346,193)
    #Reading in image
    image = cv.imread(path)

    #Some Preprocessing- splitting channels then applying
    gaussian blur to eliminate noise
    (B,G,R) = cv.split(image)
    red = cv.GaussianBlur(R,(3,3),0)

    #Finding max intensity and drawing a circle around it
    r = 50
    cv.circle(image,cCenter,r,(255,0,0),4)

    #Creates mask to calculate intensity
    mask = np.zeros_like(R)
    cv.circle(mask,cCenter,r,255,-1)

    #calculates average and stdev, seperates and rounds values
    avg_std = cv.meanStdDev(R,mask=mask)
    avg = round(avg_std[0][0][0],2)
    std = round(avg_std[1][0][0],2)

    #Locations to move text
    x = cCenter[0]
    y = cCenter[1]

    #Puts text over the original image
    cv.putText(image,str(avg)+" +/-"+str(std),(x-80,y-
r-20),cv.FONT_HERSHEY_SIMPLEX, 0.6, (255, 255, 255), 2)

    #Displays final image
    window_name = ' '
    cv.namedWindow(window_name, cv.WND_PROP_FULLSCREEN)
    cv.setWindowProperty(window_name, cv.WND_PROP_FULLSCREEN,
cv.WINDOW_FULLSCREEN)

    cv.imshow(window_name, image)
    cv.waitKey(0)
    cv.destroyAllWindows()
    return

```

```
picam2 = Picamera2()
camera_config =
picam2.create_preview_configuration(controls={"ExposureTime": 7000000,
"FrameDurationLimits": (7000000,7000000), "AnalogueGain": 1})
picam2.configure(camera_config)
picam2.start()
```

```
imagenname = 0
while imagenname != 'stop.jpg':
    imagenname = input('input file name: ')
    if '.jpg' not in imagenname:
        imagenname = imagenname+'.jpg'
    if imagenname != 'stop.jpg':

        picam2.capture_file(imagenname)
        time.sleep(1)

        ImageAnalysis(imagenname)
```